

RESIDUAL STRESSES AND THE STRENGTH OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Summary

Possible relationships between residual stresses in metal matrix composites and observed constraint effects are discussed. Residual stresses measured by X-ray diffraction can be described in terms of a simple continuum model if stress relaxation accompanies deformation and hardening. The model demonstrates that the flow stress is split into separate mean stress and friction stress components arising from elastic and plastic heterogeneity. The rate of stress relaxation depends on the size of the inclusions.

1. Introduction

The origin of residual stresses in metal matrix composites is the phase misfits of inelastic strain which arise during the preparation and application of the material. For example, cooling is often involved in the preparation and this causes misfits of thermal contraction. Potentially the misfits are associated with very large thermal residual stresses. In reality the stresses are relieved to varying degrees by stress relaxation mechanisms, such as plastic flow, sliding or decohesion at interfaces and microcracking. More generally, phase misfits are also caused by plastic pre-strain and crystal transformation. The patterns of unrelaxed residual stresses can in general be decomposed into quasi-uniform long-range stresses and non-uniform short-range stresses, in accordance with the Saint Venant principle. In applications of composites it is usually not possible to exploit the strength of the strong phase fully without permitting some plastic flow in the weaker phase. Consequently the patterns of residual stress must change during the application, and these changes are closely related to the strength of the composite.

It is not straightforward to describe the residual stresses and analyse their effects. This is partly because of the complexity of the various stress relaxation mechanisms and partly because of constraint effects, as we shall see. Thus the difficulties are only to a limited extent analytical ones. A simple mathematical analysis could not provide a complete description: for example, chemical effects on the strength of interfaces could interfere. Under such complex circumstances it seems that initially a theory of residual stresses should not aim for completeness. It should attempt to give a rigorous description of the common features of residual stresses while leaving room for experimental information on stress relaxation and constrained flow.

The present approach (1-5) is to combine a rigorous mean field theory of thermoelastic deformation with the idea of an "effectively" uniform unrelaxed plastic strain in the matrix, ϵ_p^* . It seems futile to try to calculate ϵ_p^* , so its numerical value is left for experimental measurement. As a theory the approach is then incomplete; but the framework is rigorous, so the approach is not an exercise in curve fitting. The concept of ϵ_p^* is shared with Ashby's (6) continuum model and its modifications by energy (7) and stress (8) analyses in terms of Eshelby's general ideas (9). Essentially, the present approach is a further modification of the stress analysis to clarify in rigorous terms the role played by elastic heterogeneity. The same modification was suggested for the energy analysis (10-12). It is convenient to refer collectively to all the analyses sharing the basic idea of ϵ_p^* as the continuum model.

Here we shall consider some of the available in-situ X-ray diffraction data on residual stresses in metal matrix composites (section 2) in terms of the continuum model (section 3). A new expression will be derived (section 4) for the overall tensile hardening rate of a composite displaying both matrix hardening and stress relaxation. The emphasis will be on the physical basis of the strength of metal matrix composites and the role of internal and residual stress.

2. Constraint Effects

The individual phases in a composite are not free to deform like isolated crystals and the question whether this constraint affects their in-situ constitutive equations significantly is central in the physics of composite materials. Careful experiments demonstrate that metal matrix composites display marked effects which are inexplicable in terms of the established mechanics of composites alone, one is forced to invoke some kind of synergism. These "constraint effects" will be described here and their possible explanations in terms of residual stresses will be discussed.

Particle composites

It is instructive first to consider Krock's (13) particle composites, prepared by infiltration of tungsten powder compacts with liquid copper. Potentially the thermal misfit strain developed on cooling from the infiltration temperature (1150°C) to room temperature is ~ 1.5%, and it corresponds to a large hydrostatic compression of the tungsten particles. This compression will in part be plastically accommodated by generation of dislocation tangles around the tungsten particles. The remaining misfit will be elastically accommodated, giving rise to thermal residual stresses. Additional components of stress inside the particles (inclusions) will arise, according to Eshelby's theory (9), when the composite is subjected to external mechanical loads: for all loads the particles will contain "elastic" inclusion stresses due to the composite's elastic heterogeneity; and "plastic" inclusion stresses will build up when the matrix starts to flow plastically around the inclusions. For a definition of the terms "elastic" and "plastic" stress the reader is referred to (2). These three components of the inclusion stress can all be identified experimentally by X-ray diffraction (14) and correlated, at sufficiently large strains, with fracture of the inclusions or with interface decohesion. Their counterparts in the matrix are closely related to the in-situ constitutive equations for plastic flow in the matrix, as we shall see from the experiments.

The residual stresses do not affect the overall elastic constants of the composite. These must lie between rigorous bounds irrespective of particle size and distribution. The Hashin-Shtrikman bounds for the composite's shear and bulk moduli, μ_c and κ_c , can be written (1) in the form

$$\mu_c = \mu_1 / \left(1 + \frac{f_2 D'}{1 - f_2 \gamma D'} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\kappa_c = \kappa_1 / \left(1 + \frac{f_2 C'}{1 - f_2 \beta C'} \right) \quad (2)$$

using Eshelby's (9) general ideas and a simple mean field approximation, see next section. The subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the phases, f_2 is the volume fraction of phase 2 and expressions for β , γ , C' and D' can be found in (1). It should be noted that eqs. 1 and 2 only provide bounds in the special case $(\mu_1 - \mu_2)(\kappa_1 - \kappa_2) \geq 0$ considered by Hashin and Shtrikman (16). Using the classical extremum principles, Walpole (17) covered the general case, and his analysis reveals that in order to supply bounds eqs. 1 and 2 must be modified when $(\mu_1 - \mu_2)(\kappa_1 - \kappa_2) \leq 0$, see (3). The combination of Foreman's (18) elastic constants for "effectively" isotropic copper and Lowrie and Gonas' (19) constants for tungsten represent the case $(\mu_1 - \mu_2)(\kappa_1 - \kappa_2) \leq 0$ (a small correction to the numerical values of A, B, and C calculated in (3) should be made). Figure 1 shows Walpole's bounds for Young's modulus, $E = 9\kappa\mu/(3\kappa + \mu)$, calculated on the basis of Foreman, Lowrie and Gonas' elastic constants for copper and tungsten.

Fig. 1. Experimental measurements of the overall Young's modulus for copper-matrix tungsten-fibre particle composites. The shaded area represents bounds set by rigorous composite mechanics (17) for an ideal system with elastic phases and interfaces strong enough to transmit any stress component without sliding or decohesion.

The bounds are seen to be higher than the experimental values. This result depends somewhat on the choice of elastic constants in the calculation: Krock uses $E = 0.344$ TPa for tungsten and this reduces the deviation a bit; but a small overestimate remains, at least for $f < 0.6$. This would be consistent with some sliding or decohesion at the interfaces; but it is perhaps even more likely that the measured strain includes some localized microflow caused by thermal residual stresses. Sakaki, Sugimoto and Fukuzato (20) discussed this type of behaviour in the case of ferrite-martensite particle composites (dual phase steels), in which there is an increase of the particle volume during the austenite-martensite transformation. It seems

clear enough that the phenomenon of "continuous yielding" in the dual phase steels is related to this transformation expansion and the associated residual stresses.

The macroplastic behaviour of metal matrix particle composites involves strong constraint effect: Krock (15) finds that iron-nickel with more than 60 vol. pct. tungsten particles of $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ diameter shows ductilities in excess of 25% tensile plastic strain at room temperature. This is many times the ductility of free tungsten. Two radically different explanations have been suggested for this type of behaviour: the isostrain model and Ashby's continuum model. The isostrain model attempts to explain the high ductility of the composite as an indirect effect of the hydrostatic compressive residual stress generated inside the tungsten particles by cooling during fabrication. It is suggested (21) that the hydrostatic stress enhances the ductility of the tungsten particles to such an extent that they can preserve compatibility with the matrix by plastic flow. By contrast, according to Ashby's continuum model, as applied to dual phase steels (22,23), the particles remain plastically undeformable. The effect instead arises from a change in the flow pattern in the matrix dictated by the particles. An increased rate of dislocation storage associated with this change leads to an overall workhardening rate which increases more rapidly with decrease of particle size than does the flow stress. It follows from the Considère criterion that the ductility is high for small particles, say particle sizes of a few microns. The continuum model seems well supported by the experimental data on dual phase steels, while the tungsten particle data is perhaps too scarce for a qualified decision. In general the ductility is, of course, limited by particle cracking and interface decohesion.

Dispersion strengthened metals are similar to particle composites, but different in the range of sizes and volume fractions of the particles, typically for dispersions one has $f < 0.1$ and $d < 1 \mu\text{m}$. The continuum model was initially developed for dispersion strengthening, where it seems a realistic approximation, unless the plastic strain or the particle size are too small. Typically, for $\epsilon_p < 0.05$ and $d < 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ it becomes necessary to consider the interaction of discrete slip lines with individual particles. The latest discussion of the limitations of the continuum model for dispersion strengthening can be found in the paper by Pedersen and Brown (24).

Fibre composites

During plastic elongation in the fibre direction of a continuous fibre composite a strong constraint effect modifies the constitutive equation of the matrix. The first and most direct experiment is due to Cheskis and Heckel (25). They subjected a thin copper-tungsten fibre composite to tensile deformation in a straining device which permitted simultaneous strain readings from a strain-gauge and an X-ray diffractometer. Figure 2 shows their results. Here ϵ_{SG} is the overall tensile strain of the composite, read from the strain gauge, and ϵ_{XR} is the mean tensile lattice strain for copper and tungsten, read from the diffractometer.

The slope of the ϵ_{XR} versus ϵ_{SG} curve for the matrix displays a marked change, which Cheskis and Heckel interpret as the transition from deformation with elastic fibres and elastic matrix (stage I) to deformation with elastic fibres but elastic-plastic matrix (stage II). It is immediately apparent that there is a strong constraint effect: the slope for the matrix in stage II is a large fraction of its stage I slope. In other words, the constrained matrix workhardens much faster than a free matrix, which would display a slope of only a fraction of a per cent of the elastic slope.

Fig. 2 In-situ X-ray diffraction measurements (25) of lattice strains (ϵ_{XR}) and overall strains (ϵ_{SG}) in polycrystalline copper with 20 vol. pct. tungsten fibres. The ϵ_p^* is identified with the source of residual stresses in the continuum model, see text.

Theories suggested for this type of constraint effect may be divided broadly into two groups: matrix substructure models and residual stress models. Differences in thermal contraction during fabrication generate dislocation tangles in the matrix and these tangles act as obstacles to slip. According to the matrix substructure models this should largely account for Cheskis and Heckel's constraint effect. The residual stress models, on the other hand, attribute the constraint effect to the interaction between mobile dislocations and residual stresses, represented in different ways. It is important to note that the residual stress models refer to the build-up of the non-uniform Saint Venant type residual stresses during deformation. The idea that a multi-axial matrix mean stress might explain the effect is ruled out experimentally by subsequent X-ray studies by Cheskis and Heckel (26,27): they show first that a longitudinal mean matrix stress $\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_M$ parallel to the fibres shifts the entire stress-strain for the composite along the stress axis while a transverse mean matrix stress $\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_M$ adds to or subtracts from the longitudinal mean matrix stress. These observations may be summarized by a Tresca type flow criterion

$$\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_M - \langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_M = 2\tau_M \quad (3)$$

where $2\tau_M$ is the mean in-situ matrix yield stress. Now, the possibility of explaining the constraint effect in terms of multiaxial mean stresses is excluded, because Cheskis and Heckel (26) show that while considerable values of $\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_M$ can be observed (in Al-B), the actual changes (needed to account for the matrix hardening rate) of $\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_M$ with tensile deformation were always negligible. This observation confirms Kelly and Lilholt's (28) earlier conclusion based on Hill's (29) rigorous bounds, see section 4.

With continued elongation of the composite a transition occurs to stage III, associated with yield or fracture of the fibres. When f exceeds a critical value f_{crit} (30) the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of the composite exceeds the UTS of the unreinforced matrix. The rule of mixtures

$$\sigma_{UC} = f \sigma_{uF} + (1-f)\sigma_{uFM} \quad (4)$$

then usually provides a fair approximation to the UTS of the composite, here σ_{uF} is the UTS of the free fibres and σ_{uFM} is the flow stress of the free matrix at the maximum uniform strain of the fibres. This is exemplified in Fig. 3, where $f_{crit} \sim 0.05$. However, the observed in-situ matrix hardening

must affect the σ_{UFM} term, probably increasing σ_{UC} by $\sim 20\%$ irrespective of f . Further constraint effects may arise at fibre necks (31), where transverse tensile stresses in the matrix act to oppose necking of the fibres, thereby increasing the ductility and UTS of the composite.

Fig. 3. Tensile strength measurements (32) on polycrystalline copper with various contents of continuous and discontinuous tungsten fibres.

The fibre aspect ratio does not affect the 0.2% yield stress, see Fig. 3, but it has a strong effect on the UTS. Harris and Ramani (32) show that short fibre composites display a characteristic "yield drop". The fibre orientation is also important, e.g. Harris and Ramani found that randomly oriented fibres had no strengthening effect. Finally, the fibre diameter plays an important role, as discussed in detail in section 4 for fibres with $d > 10\mu\text{m}$. As in the case of particle composites the continuum approximation seems to be successful and its limitations in this application are not as yet clear. One would expect the limitations to be less severe than in the case of particle composites, because even very thin fibres are of macroscopic length. Some commercial systems with very thin fibres ($d \sim 0.1\mu\text{m}$) may derive their UTS from indirect effects of the fibres. Arsenault (33) suggests that thin SiC fibres in 6061 aluminium stabilize a high dislocation density and a small subgrain size in the matrix and he attributes the dominant strengthening effect to this substructure. However, further work is required at low strains where residual stress effects may dominate.

3. Continuum Model

When an elastically heterogeneous material is under external stress it will contain a component of internal stress which is proportional to the external stress (9,2,14). The source of this "elastic" stress is the misfits of elastic strain caused by the difference between the elastic constants of the phases. In-situ diffraction measures the sum of the external stress, the mean elastic stress and the mean residual ("thermal" and "plastic") stress. Therefore, to make progress in studies of residual stresses in composites it is necessary to be able to decompose the measured mean stresses into their separate components of applied-, elastic- and residual stress. Possible methods for this decomposition may be developed on the basis of the continuum model, as outlined below.

Continuum approximation

Compatibility demands for elongation or compression in the fibre direction (X_3) of a metal with continuous fibres that the elastic and plastic mean strains satisfy

$$\langle \epsilon_{33}^P \rangle_C + \langle \epsilon_{33}^E \rangle_C = \langle \epsilon_{33}^P \rangle_M + \langle \epsilon_{33}^E \rangle_M = \langle \epsilon_{33}^P \rangle_F + \langle \epsilon_{33}^E \rangle_F \quad (5)$$

where the indices refer to plastic (P), elastic (E), composite (C), matrix (M) and fibres (F). In a real composite plastic flow is non-uniform at the level of dislocations and there will be gradients of slip (6) at the level of phase sizes. In addition, stress relaxation may occur by interface sliding and decohesion, plastic flow or cracking of phases, buckling of fibres etc. All these processes act to relieve stresses, so let us examine if their overall effects can be modelled simply by a stress-free strain $\langle \epsilon_{33}^P \rangle_F$ in the fibres. This idea and eq. 5 lead to the misfit parameter

$$\epsilon_P^* = \langle \epsilon_{33}^P \rangle_M - \langle \epsilon_{33}^P \rangle_F = \langle \epsilon_{33}^E \rangle_F - \langle \epsilon_{33}^E \rangle_M \quad (6)$$

We require of ϵ_P^* that it must behave like Eshelby's (9) transformation strain, otherwise it would not be a useful representation of the sources of residual stress. The behaviour of ϵ_P^* will therefore be examined in rigorous terms: we shall adopt Nye's (34) matrix notation in which pairs of Latin subscripts ij are replaced by single Greek subscripts α according to the scheme

ij	11	22	33	23/32	13/31	12/21
α	1	2	3	4	5	6

and subsequently dropped. Thus $\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_\alpha = \sigma$, and similarly for the strain tensor, where factors of 2 have to be introduced. Nye's notation displays the symmetry of Eshelby's S tensor very neatly, for spheroidal fibres along x_3 we have

$$S_{ijkl} = S_{\alpha\beta} = S = \begin{pmatrix} \bullet & \bullet & \bullet & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \bullet & \bullet & \bullet & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \bullet & \bullet & \bullet & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \bullet & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \bullet & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \times \end{pmatrix} \begin{matrix} \bullet & \text{non-zero} \\ \bullet & \text{zero} \\ \bullet & \text{equal} \\ \times & S_{11} - S_{12} \end{matrix} \quad (7)$$

In the absence of experimental evidence we shall assume that the appropriate transformation strain tensor has non-zero components ϵ_{33}^T and $\epsilon_{11}^T = \epsilon_{22}^T$ (all other $\epsilon_{ij}^T = 0$) and discuss the continuum approximation that

$$\epsilon_{33}^T = -\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{22}^T = -\epsilon_P^* \quad (8)$$

hoping that eq. 8 will be compatible with the dominant features of the experimental behaviour. For elastically heterogeneous composites it would be convenient if ϵ^T could simply be replaced by Eshelby's equivalent transformation strain

$$\epsilon_2^{T*} = K_{12} (L_2 \epsilon_2^T + (L_1 - L_2) \epsilon^U) \quad (9)$$

as presented in (2), where the subscripts 1 and 2 now do not refer to the coordinate axis, they refer to matrix (1) and inclusions (2). The K_{12} is a 6x6 matrix which depends on Eshelby's S matrix and the stiffness matrices L_1 and L_2 . The ϵ^U is problematic at first: in Eshelby's theory it is a uniform elastic strain applied to the matrix at infinity. The counterpart of ϵ^U in the finite composite is the non-uniform surrounding elastic strain ϵ^S (1), which obviously cannot be known in detail if phase volume fractions f_1 and $f_2 = 1-f_1$ are the only phase structural information available.

Fig. 4. The mean field theory for "elastic" and residual stresses and overall deformation features an elastic-plastic matrix with a random array of parallel inclusions. The inclusions are all ellipsoids of the same shape, but they may differ in size, see (1-4).

Mean field approximation

In the style of the continuum approximation one might now try the mean field approximation that $\epsilon^U = \langle \epsilon^S \rangle_C$, and check whether the resulting mean field theory can be reconciled with the established mechanics of composite materials. For two-phase composites this leads to

$$\epsilon_2^{T^*} = J_1 K_{12} (L_2 \epsilon_2^T + (L_1 - L_2) M_1 \sigma^A) \quad (10)$$

where J_1 is a 6x6 matrix given in (2). Now, according to the equilibrium requirement $\epsilon_2^{T^*}$ adds the term $f_2 \epsilon_2^{T^*}$ to the composite's mean strain. It follows that expressions for the overall compliance matrix M^C can be written directly from eq. 10 as

$$M^C = (I + f_2 J_1 K_{12} (L_1 - L_2)) M_1 \quad (11)$$

see (2). Furthermore, the elastic-plastic counterpart of Levin's thermo-elastic relations follow (2) as

$$\epsilon^{PC} = \epsilon^{P1} + (M^C - M_1) L_1 (L_1 - L_2)^{-1} L_2 (\epsilon^{P2} - \epsilon^{P1}) \quad (12)$$

The apparently simplistic mean field approximation is therefore not incompatible with the established mechanics of composite materials, it is in fact a key feature in Walpole's (17) unified formulation for elastic composites. Thus it can be shown (3) that the mean field theory for inelastic composites is equivalent with a combination of the general formulations by Walpole (17) and Laws (35). The important new result is that the mean field theory provides an expression for the in-situ equivalent transformation strain of the fibres. Figure 5 illustrates the relationship between the mean field theory and the established mechanics of composites: the shaded areas are bounded by curves representing the mean field approximation. For spherical inclusions ($c/a=1$) and continuous fibres ($c/a \rightarrow \infty$) the boundaries coincide with rigorous bounds of the Hashin-Hill-Shtrikman type. The self-consistent approximation (36) lies in the shaded area, the simplistic Cox (37) approximation lies outside. For details the reader is referred to the discussion in (3).

Fig. 5. Elastic moduli $E_{33} = 1/M_{33}$ and $G_{13} = 1/M_{13}$ for epoxy with short fibres parallel with the X_3 axis (spheroids, with $c > a = b$). Shaded areas represents predictions by the mean field theory which coincide with rigorous bounds. The large separation of the bounds reflects the strong elastic heterogeneity of glass-epoxy.

The longitudinal plastic strain ϵ_{33}^{PC} of the composite can, following eq. 12, be written in the form

$$\epsilon_{33}^{PC} = C\epsilon_{33}^{P1} + (1-C)\epsilon_{33}^{P2} \quad (13)$$

where C is calculated from generalised versions of eqs. 11 and 12, see (3). For the elastically homogeneous case C is simply the matrix volume fraction f_1 . The plastic strains in eq. 13 are the continuum approximations

$$\epsilon_{33}^{P1} = \langle \epsilon_{33}^P \rangle_M = \epsilon_P \quad (14)$$

$$\epsilon_{33}^{P2} = \langle \epsilon_{33}^P \rangle_F \quad (15)$$

By combining eqs. 6, 13, 14 and 15 one finds

$$\epsilon_{33}^{PC} = \epsilon_P - (1-C)\epsilon_P^* \quad (16)$$

The essential feature of the mean field theory is that it delivers rigorous approximations to residual and other internal stresses within the framework of the continuum model. These approximations are proportional to ϵ^{T*} and according to eq. 10 the corresponding mean matrix stress must then contain elastic terms proportional to σ^A and inelastic terms proportional to ϵ_P^* . For $\epsilon_{33}^A = \sigma^A$ and all other $\sigma_{ij}^A = 0$ we can write

$$\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle_M = A_1 \epsilon_P^* + B_1 \sigma^A \quad (17)$$

$$\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_M = A_2 \epsilon_P^* + B_2 \sigma^A \quad (18)$$

$$\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_M = A_3 \epsilon_P^* + B_3 \sigma^A + \sigma^A \quad (19)$$

where A_i and B_i can be calculated using the results of (3). According to eq. 8 we have $A_1 = A_2$ and $B_1 = B_2$.

Analysis of diffraction data

With the mean field theory we are in a position to work out the rigorous implications of dealing with ϵ_p^* as if it were an Eshelby type transformation strain: the diffraction data of Fig. 2 provide the composite's tensile flow stress as

$$\sigma^F = f \sigma_W^{XR} + (1-f) \sigma_{Cu}^{XR} \tag{20}$$

where σ_W^{XR} and σ_{Cu}^{XR} are the mean longitudinal phase stresses calculated from the measured lattice strains. Figure 6 shows σ^F as a function of the plastic elongation of the composite, calculated as

$$\epsilon_{33}^{PC} = \epsilon_{SG} - \sigma^F/E_C \tag{21}$$

where E_C is the composite's effective longitudinal Young's modulus and ϵ_{SG} is its total strain.

The mean matrix stress is seen to be split into approximately equal elastic and plastic components, $B_3\sigma^F$ and $A_3\epsilon_p^*$, and the constraint effect becomes apparent: the flow stress is clearly not just the stress required to overcome the elastic and plastic mean stresses. A substantial matrix friction stress, of magnitude comparable to the mean stresses, must be overcome in addition. And this additional stress is indeed a friction stress and not a transverse mean matrix stress: according to the mean field theory $\langle\sigma_{22}\rangle_M$ amounts to only 5 to 10% of $\langle\sigma_{33}\rangle_M$, see (4).

Fig. 6. When applied to Cheskis and Heckel's (25) X-ray evidence the continuum model shows that the linear stage II curve for Cu-20 vol. pct W is split into an "elastic" mean stress ($B\sigma^F$), a "plastic" residual stress ($A_3\epsilon_p^*$) and a constrained matrix flow stress.

Fig. 7. The continuum model implies that the build-up of residual stress $A_3 \epsilon_p^*$ during deformation is reduced by stress relaxation.

The continuum model also implies that stress relaxation occurs throughout stage II: in a perfectly unrelaxed composite the plastic strain in the matrix ϵ_p would be identical to ϵ_p^* . In relaxed composites $\epsilon_p^* < \epsilon_p$ and the values of ϵ_p corresponding to ϵ_p^* can be calculated from simultaneous measurements of ϵ_{XR} and ϵ_{SG} using eqs. 16, 20 and 21. The values calculated from Cheskis and Heckel's copper-tungsten data are shown in Fig. 7. Stress relaxation clearly takes place in stage II, in such a way that ϵ_p^* varies approximately linearly with ϵ_p .

Fig. 8. The continuum model provides a consistent account of the X-ray data. The small systematic differences between σ_{Cu}^{XR} and $\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_M$ lies within the uncertainty arising from the use of isotropic elasticity.

Finally, it is possible to check the internal consistency of the continuum model: the total mean matrix stress during flow is, according to eq. 19, the sum of $A_3 \epsilon_p^*$, $B_3 \sigma^F$ and σ^F . This sum should be identical to the value σ_{Cu}^{XR} measured by diffraction. Excellent agreement is found, see Fig. 8. Thus it appears that the X-ray evidence justifies the continuum model and allows us to consider its possibilities as a theoretical framework for experimental studies of the strength of metal matrix fibre composites.

4. Relaxation and Strength

We shall now return to the problem of the in-situ matrix hardening in metal matrix fibre composites, which is still incompletely understood and which may hold the key to a physically based theory of the strength of these materials. In section 2 we divided the theories of in-situ matrix hardening into two groups: matrix substructure models and residual stress models. Here we examine the available data on the tensile strength of copper with tungsten fibres in terms of the continuum model and discuss the possibility of making an empirical decision between the theories.

Elastic and plastic friction

According to the continuum model the internal stresses are proportional to the equivalent transformation strain ϵ^{T^*} and this means that they can be split into a plastic component proportional to ϵ_p^* and an elastic component proportional to σ^A . This split refers both to the non-uniform Saint Venant type stresses and to the quasi-uniform mean stresses. The in-situ hardening is in the residual stress model supposed to be governed by the non-uniform stresses and in view of the characteristic linearity of stage II this would suggest that

$$2\tau_M = \alpha \epsilon_p^* + \beta \sigma^A + \delta \quad (22)$$

as discussed in (4). The "plastic friction", $\alpha \epsilon_p^*$, and the "elastic friction", $\beta \sigma^A$, would dominate if the residual stress model is adequate for the system. We note that at this stage α , β and δ are phenomenological coefficients, to be checked and measured experimentally. This should not be misinterpreted, a physical theory of the in-situ hardening, of course, remains the ultimate goal.

The coefficient δ represents friction associated with the matrix substructure (dislocation tangles, grain-boundaries, particles etc.) and δ would dominate if the matrix substructure model is adequate for the system. The initial value of δ represents the matrix strengthening introduced during fabrication of the composite. For example, Chawla and Metzger's (38,39) etch pit work on copper single crystals with tungsten fibres show that differential thermal shrinkage during fabrication generates a dislocation cell structure in the matrix. The etch pit work also demonstrates that when the matrix hardens during a tensile test of the composite this is accompanied by an increase of its dislocation density. However, this observation is not critical, it would be expected in the residual stress model as well as in the matrix substructure model. A wider discussion of the experimental behaviour of metal matrix fibre composites is therefore needed before one may hope to reach a qualified decision.

The residual stress model has the advantage that it allows one to predict the approximate values of α and β from the physics of plastic flow in the case of single crystal matrices. The prediction is based on an analysis of the reduction (source-shortening) with plastic strain of the effective inter-fibre spacing due to moving dislocations being forced away from the fibres by repulsive local stresses. The approach is due to Brown and Stobbs (8) who applied it to dispersion strengthened metals where source-shortening is caused by Orowan loops, represented by ϵ_p^* . Brown and Clarke (40) applied the approach to dilute fibre composites, which behave essentially like the dispersion strengthened metals. Brown and Clarke's estimate of the source-shortening effect corresponds to

$$\alpha = \frac{5}{2\pi} f \mu_1 \left(K \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1} \right) \quad \text{for } f < 0.1 \quad (23)$$

where K depends in a complicated way on the elastic constants of fibres and matrix and on the orientation of the slip system relative to the fibres. The source-shortening approach can also be fitted into the present version of the continuum model, and this provides estimates of both α and β for arbitrary f values (5). The essential features of these estimates are that α and β are both nearly proportional to f and independent of the fibre diameter.

Low strain tensile strength

Let us examine the available data on the tensile strength of copper tungsten fibre composites which cover fibre diameters in the range from $d = 10 \mu\text{m}$ to $230 \mu\text{m}$. The data include tests on fine-grained matrices in hot-pressed systems (25,41,32) as well as tests on single crystal matrices in vacuum infiltrated systems (28,38,39). Comparisons between these two modifications of the copper-tungsten system are of interest, because systematic differences might be anticipated, such as hot-pressed composites showing larger δ values and poorer interface cohesion.

For stage II of the tensile stress-strain curve the data are provided in the form of "derived matrix curves", i.e. plots of the mean matrix stress

$$\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_M = (\sigma^F - fE_F \langle \epsilon_{33} \rangle_C) / (1-f) \quad (24)$$

versus the total strain of the composite. The tensile flow stress σ^F can be recovered from these curves and eq. 21 then provides the composite's plastic strain ϵ_{33}^{PC} . With information on the rate of stress relaxation $d\epsilon_p^*/d\epsilon_p$ one may then calculate the plastic strain ϵ_p in the matrix using eq. 16. An in-situ stress-strain curve of τ_M versus e_p can then be calculated, where

$$\tau_M \cong \langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_M / 2 \quad (25)$$

$$e_p = 2\epsilon_p \quad (26)$$

We note that eq. 25 is approximative. This is because the small contribution from the transverse mean matrix stress (see eq. 3) to the mean matrix friction stress τ_M is neglected. However, the mean field theory and X-ray diffraction show that the approximation is better than 10%.

In the absence of information on stress relaxation, apart from the value suggested by X-ray diffraction (Fig. 7), a value of $2/3$ for $d\epsilon_p^*/d\epsilon_p$ was assumed for all the present calculations. In-situ stress-strain curves thus calculated for fine grained polycrystalline copper are presented in Fig. 9. An approximately linear stage II extends to $e_p \sim 2 \times 10^{-3}$ and the in-situ matrix hardening rate in units of the elastic shear modulus of copper

$$\theta/\mu = \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{d\tau_M}{de_p} \quad (27)$$

decreases from a value of ~ 0.8 to ~ 0.2 when the fibre diameter increases from $d = 10 \mu\text{m}$ to $48 \mu\text{m}$. The magnitude of θ/μ is consistent with the X-ray evidence: $\theta/\mu \sim 0.5$ for $f = 0.2$ and $d = 25 \mu\text{m}$. In-situ curves calculated from Kelly and Lilholt's data for single crystal copper matrix also display a stage II range extending to $e_p \sim 2 \times 10^{-3}$ for $f = 0.38$ and $d = 10 \mu\text{m}$, with

Fig. 9. In-situ stress-strain curves for fine-grained copper containing tungsten fibres of different diameter. The curves were calculated from data by Lee and Harris (41), assuming a relaxation rate of 3/2 irrespective of the fibre diameter.

$\theta/\mu \sim 0.8$. Free single crystals, by comparison, show maximum values of $\theta/\mu \sim 0.003$ in tensile tests. Very strong modifications of the matrix substructure are indeed required to account for this discrepancy of 2-3 orders of magnitude. It is possible to reach values of $\theta/\mu \sim 0.3$ in tension-compression tests on free single crystals at constant amplitudes of $\epsilon_p < 10^{-3}$ (42), but only after a cumulative plastic shear of $4N\epsilon_p \sim 10$ ($N =$ cycle number). Also, very high θ/μ values are associated with the roundedness of in-situ stress-strain curves in the microyield range, but this range is $\epsilon_p < 3 \times 10^{-4}$, according to Chawla and Metzger's (38,39) observations. Continuum plasticity also suggests a microyield range of $\epsilon_p < 3 \times 10^{-4}$ (43, 28).

These observations imply that the fibres control matrix hardening in stage II through residual stresses rather than through the matrix substructure produced in the fabrication process. In addition, the limits of the stage II phenomenon appear to be imposed by residual stresses and elastic stresses: the transition to stage III in a tensile test is found (28) to be associated with yield of the fibres in the case of a single crystal matrix. However, we saw from Fig. 9 that the range of stage II appears to be about the same, whether the matrix is a single crystal or a polycrystal. Thus it appears that the fibres control the onset of stage III irrespective of the matrix substructure. The disappearance of stage II for fibre contents greater than $f \sim 0.5$ (see Fig. 10) is at present less clear. It is presumably associated with very strong elastic friction. However, while the theory of τ_M needs developing before a critical check of this idea may become possible, the observed in-situ hardening rates are fairly consistently scattered around the curve

$$\theta/\mu = \frac{f}{1-f} \quad (28)$$

as Fig. 10 shows. Kelly and Lilholt (28) first recognized the physics implied by eq. 28: in order to reconcile their measurements for copper with 10 μm fibres with Hill's (29) rigorous mechanics they were forced to the conclusion that, in effect, a volume fraction $f/(1-f)$ of the matrix stays elastic while the remainder is ideally plastic.

Fig. 10. Summary of the in-situ tensile matrix hardening rates derived on the basis of the continuum model from experimental data on copper-tungsten fibre composites.

Stress relaxation and size effects

We saw that stress relaxation had to be invoked in order for the continuum model to be compatible with the X-ray data. A similar feature emerges when the model is applied to the tensile test data: there is a marked effect of fibre diameter on the stage II hardening rate. In the case of a polycrystalline matrix this is clear from Lee and Harris' data in Figs. 9 and 10. In the case of a single crystal matrix Kelly and Lilholt found that the elastic portion of the matrix amounted to a volume fraction of only $0.65 f/(1-f)$ when $d = 20 \mu\text{m}$, as opposed to $f/(1-f)$ when $d = 20 \mu\text{m}$. Yet, according to the residual stress theory the coefficients α and β in τ_M are independent of d . In other words, the residual stress theory predicts from the observations that the stress relaxation rate $d\varepsilon_p^*/d\varepsilon_p$ depends on the fibre diameter. Otherwise the residual stress theory of τ_M would have to be abandoned.

It is possible to get a quantitative idea of the effect of the fibre diameter on stress relaxation from the tensile data. By combining eqs. 3, 18, 19 and 22 we can write

$$\sigma^F = (A+\alpha) \varepsilon_p^* + (B+\beta)\sigma^F + \delta \quad (29)$$

and by differentiating eqs. 16 and 29 we find the stage II hardening rate for the composite as

$$\theta_c = \frac{d\sigma^F}{d\epsilon_{33}^{PC}} = \left(\frac{d\sigma^F}{d\epsilon_p^*} \right) / \left(\frac{d\epsilon_{33}^{PC}}{d\epsilon_p^*} \right) \quad (30)$$

$$= \frac{A+\alpha}{(1-B-\beta)(d\epsilon_p^*/d\epsilon_p^* - 1 + C)}$$

which describes the competing effects of matrix hardening and stress relaxation. In the hypothetical case of no hardening ($\alpha=0$, $\beta=0$) and no relaxation ($d\epsilon_p^*/d\epsilon_p=1$) eq. 30 reduces to the θ_o expression plotted in Fig. 2 of (2), i.e. the sum curve for elastic and plastic mean stress, called θ_o in (3). The present comprehensive analysis of the data available on tensile stage II in copper-tungsten confirms that the measured θ_c values are scattered around 3/2 times θ_o . Now, let us suppose that the experimental value of $d\epsilon_p^*/d\epsilon_p = 0.75$ (Fig. 7) for Cheskis and Heckel' composite ($d=25 \mu\text{m}$) is approximately the relaxation rate in Lee and Harris' composites with $d = 20 \mu\text{m}$. Quantitative agreement between the θ_c measurements and eq. 30 then requires that $d\epsilon_p^*/d\epsilon_p \sim 0.4$ for $d = 48 \mu\text{m}$.

It is clear that a variety of stress relaxation mechanisms are possible, depending on the composite system and on modifications of the system. The relaxation rate is usually temperature dependent (44), and residual stresses may certainly be reduced by high temperature exposure of the unloaded composite. Such experiments by Pattnaik and Lawley (45) on hotpressed Al-Fe fibre composites suggest that the stage II flow stress is changed while θ_c remains unchanged. This is consistent with the residual stress theory, but it also has to be mentioned that Pattnaik and Lawley found no significant change of the matrix substructure. Chemical changes in the fibre-matrix interface, however, reduced the stress for transition to stage III in the high temperature exposed composite. The continuum model implies that stress relaxation and overall deformation are closely related, and here the most striking example is perhaps the "length memory effect" demonstrated by Khan and Stohr (46).

5. Concluding Remarks

The ideas reviewed here are suggested by a combination of rigorous theoretical principles and experimental observations of residual stresses and the short term tensile strength of metals and metal matrix composites. However, it would appear that the continuum model has considerable potential as a physically based theory of composites for a much wider range of phenomena than the short term tensile behaviour. For example, when continued stress relaxation takes place under constant applied stress the composite should suffer recovery controlled creep: reductions of ϵ_p^* represent reductions in the plastic mean and friction stresses, which in turn allow further deformation without change of the applied stress. It also seems possible to study cyclic plasticity and fatigue in terms of the model, and this holds the immediate promise of separate measurement of plastic friction. It will be interesting to see if in fact the elastic and plastic friction in the matrix is independent of the fibre diameter and nearly proportional to the fibre volume fraction and whether τ_M can be written as a linear combination of ϵ_p^* and σ^A . Further experimental and theoretical work on well-characterised metal matrix composites and free matrix materials and fibres remains to be done to solve these current problems.

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